

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

D1: Paper on the design, characterisation and performance of newly developed broadband transfer standard sources for spectral irradiance in the ultraviolet-visible-near infrared (UV-VIS-NIR) spectral ranges, built on new-technology products (to replace current transfer standards that are based on incandescent lamps). The new standard sources will be: i) well-defined with fit-for-purpose spectral and geometric properties, and have ii) long-term stability, iii) reproducibility, iv) robustness, and v) compatibility with existing calibration facilities. The spectral irradiance unit will have transfer uncertainties as low as 0.5 % ($k = 2$) submitted to an open access peer reviewed journal

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Replacing the incandescent lamp-based standards: tuneable broadband UV LED source

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Abstract

A tuneable broadband ultraviolet (UV) LED source covering the spectral range from 255 nm to 405 nm has been designed, developed, and characterized as a potential alternative to conventional incandescent lamp-based transfer standards. The system integrates 79 commercially available UV LEDs arranged into 14 wavelength channels spanning the UVA, UVB, and UVC regions, providing continuous spectral coverage with spectral irradiance levels exceeding $1 \text{ mW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1}$ at all wavelengths. The source incorporates a multi-channel current driver and an active temperature control unit to ensure stable electrical and thermal operating conditions. Comprehensive aging and characterization measurements were carried out over approximately 110 h using an array spectrometer at a distance of 50 cm. The long-term drift was found to be on the order of 10^{-4} h^{-1} after stabilization, indicating stable long-term operation. Instability and reproducibility were evaluated after a warm-up period of 30 min. The instability remained below 0.6% for the majority of the 255 nm—405 nm range, with a maximum peak of 1.2% observed near 285 nm, while reproducibility is maintained below 1.8% for most wavelengths. These results demonstrate that the developed tuneable broadband UV LED source provides sufficient stability, flexibility, and irradiance levels for laboratory irradiance measurements and UV metrology applications.

1. Introduction

For spectral irradiance calibrations in the ultraviolet (UV) region, blackbody radiators are used as primary standard sources, while transfer standard sources are typically based on tungsten filament or deuterium lamps. Among these, deuterium lamps are widely recommended as UV irradiance sources [1, 2]. Although these lamps possess high stability and irradiance levels, difficulties in optical alignment can reduce their performance and make them difficult to handle [3].

In addition to deuterium lamps, tungsten filament lamps have been used as transfer standard sources for spectral irradiance in the UV since 1967 [4]. They have a smooth spectral irradiance distribution and stable optical output. On the other hand, they have certain metrological shortcomings such as the low irradiance level in the UV region, fragility, short life, low energy efficiency. Moreover, their production has been discontinued due to their low energy efficiency.

Therefore, there is a need for broadband, high-efficiency, and long-life lamps for UV metrology. In this regard, to overcome the limitations of traditional sources, LED technology—a significant technological advancement in the field of lighting that has already been widely adopted for the visible (VIS) region [5–9] may be preferred for developing a UV irradiance source.

There have also been studies on the development of sources operating in the UV region [10, 11]. Both studies are aimed to develop a LED based UV source having smooth broadband spectrum.

The aim of this study is to develop an LED-based tuneable broadband UV source that covers the 255 nm—405 nm range and has spectral irradiance greater than $1 \text{ mW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1}$ at every wavelength.

Section 2 of this article details the structure of the tuneable broadband UV LED source, and section 3 presents the characterization measurement results.

2. Design of the source

2.1. Wavelength selection and optical power optimization of commercial LEDs

In the initial stage, an investigation of commercially available UV LEDs was conducted. Commercial LEDs across the UVA, UVB, and UVC regions generally feature narrow bandwidths typically around 10 nm. To compensate for, the narrow-band nature and ensure continuous spectral coverage, LEDs at 14 peak wavelengths were selected to span the spectral range from 255 nm to 405 nm. UV ranges are defined as in CIE S 017:2020 [12]. Due to the limited commercial availability of LEDs emitting below 255 nm and their insufficient optical power levels for practical metrological applications, the UVC region was characterized within the 255 nm–280 nm range in this study.

While the irradiance levels of available UVC and UVB LEDs are very low and their costs remain high, the irradiance levels of the UVA LEDs identified were significantly higher than the target value of $1 \text{ mW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1}$. In the UVA region, the target spectral irradiance can be achieved with a single LED; however, the implementation requires multiple LEDs per decided wavelengths in the UVB and UVC regions to reach the required optical output.

2.2. Hardware and software/control units

The UV LED source was essentially designed in three main units: these units given in figure 1 are LED printed circuit board (PCB), multi-channel current driver and temperature control unit.

The multichannel-current driver unit and the driving and control electronics of the temperature control unit are placed in the same box called the control unit. The Peltier elements, the fans and the copper heatsink of the temperature control unit are placed behind of the LED PCB. In figure 1(b), you can see the LED PCB on the heat sink of the temperature control unit.

To build the tuneable broadband UV LED source, the LEDs given in table 1 are selected considering availability and cost. The LEDs' wavelengths are matched to the needed specifications.

Table 1. Specifications of the UV LEDs utilized.

Catalog peak WL (nm)	Optical PWR (mW)	LED quantity	Type	Output optics
255	90	5	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
265	60	6	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
275	35	11	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
285	70	6	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
295	70	5	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
310	30	13	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
325	90	13	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
340	40	11	AlGa _N	Flat quartz glass
350	100	4	AlGa _N	Quartz glass
365	1200	1	AlInGa _N	120 degree silicone lens
375	1000	1	AlGa _N	Quartz lens
385	1200	1	AlInGa _N	120 degree silicone lens
395	1200	1	AlInGa _N	120 degree silicone lens
405	1000	1	AlInGa _N	120 degree silicone lens

Figure 2. Normalized spectral power distributions of the UV LEDs with the 14 selected peak wavelengths.

However, due to the low optical power of available LEDs in the UVC and UVB regions, multiple LEDs are combined per wavelength, whereas a single LED is sufficient in the UVA region. For example, as seen in table 1, five LEDs are used for 255 nm while a single LED is used for 405 nm to achieve sufficient optical power. In total, 79 LEDs are integrated into the design to provide continuous spectral coverage across the 14 selected spectral channels. As shown in figure 1(b), the individual LEDs and LED groups are deliberately arranged on the 10 cm diameter PCB to ensure consistent spectral output for the 14 spectral channels.

Figure 2 displays the normalized spectral distribution of the 14 LED spectra. The overlap and distribution of these peaks confirm that the entire requested wavelength range is effectively covered by the integrated LED array.

A multi-channel current driver was developed based on the current ratings of the selected LEDs. Each channel can be set a current value responding to the related individual LEDs and LED groups. The current values can be set the maximum current value or any current value of the relating LED. The multi-channel current driver can give options to drive one or multi-individual LEDs and LED groups to have one or several wavelength configurations at optical output. It gives flexible usage and opportunity tuning different spectral power distributions. The system offers high operational flexibility; for instance, all 79 LEDs can be driven simultaneously to provide broad spectral coverage across all 14 wavelengths. Alternatively, specific channels can be activated independently, such as driving only the 340 nm LEDs for narrow-band output, or combining discrete wavelengths like 275 nm and 365 nm for multi-band applications.

Furthermore, a temperature control system was established to dissipate the heat generated by the LEDs and to ensure stable operation at a constant temperature. Based on the technical specifications in the LED datasheets, operating all LEDs simultaneously is projected to cause a temperature increase of approximately 90 °C. Such elevated temperatures can damage LEDs or can affect LEDs performance. Therefore, it is essential to dissipate this heat and maintain a stable operating temperature. The temperature control unit is an active temperature control system comprising a copper heat sink, Peltier elements, cooling fans and their associated driving and control electronics. The LED PCB is mounted onto a copper heat sink with high thermal conductivity to effectively dissipate the heat generated by the LEDs. To maintain thermal stability, the heat sink is cooled by two Peltier elements positioned on its reverse side, while the hot sides of these elements are cooled by two dedicated fans. The operating temperature is monitored via a negative temperature coefficient (NTC) thermistor. When the measured temperature exceeds the predefined set point of 25 °C, the Peltier elements and fans are activated to reduce the temperature until it returns to the target value. The temperature instability was achieved, with a maximum variation of 0.35 °C.

All LEDs, the multi-channel current driver unit and the temperature control unit are controlled through software. The software user interface enables inputting the current set points and monitoring the real-time applied currents for all 14 channels. Once the parameters for each channels are set and applied, the LEDs begin to emit light. The software provides real-time data logging capabilities, ensuring that the driving currents for all 14 channels and temperature values are continuously recorded during system operation.

3. Characterization measurements and results

3.1. Measurement setup and procedure

All characterization measurements were performed at 50 cm away from the source using an array spectrometer equipped with an 8 mm diameter cosine diffuser. The measurements represent absolute spectral irradiance, obtained using the array spectrometer calibrated by a national metrology institute and traceable to radiometric standards.

LEDs were subjected to an aging process exceeding 110 h. A total of 66 measurement series were performed, consisting of alternating one-hour and two-hour durations, to assess the change in optical output for each wavelength. The characterization of the source was based on the data gathered during the last 10 aging measurement series (totaling 20 h). For aging and characterization, LEDs were driven at a current slightly below their maximum ratings. The environmental conditions were $(23 \pm 2)^\circ\text{C}$ and $(45 \pm 10) \%$ rh. The temperature was set to 25 °C and was measured using an NTC sensor on the LED PCB center. Throughout the measurement series, the irradiance levels, LED PCB temperatures, and driving currents applied to the LEDs were continuously monitored and recorded.

3.2. Spectral irradiance of individual LED groups

Figure 3 presents the measured irradiance level at 50 cm as a function of wavelength for each of the 14 spectral channels. While some channels consist of a single LED, others incorporate multiple LEDs, as detailed in section 2.2.

The measured peak wavelengths of the 365 nm, 375 nm, 395 nm, and 405 nm LEDs differ significantly from the catalog values. In particular, the peaks of the 365 nm and 375 nm LEDs are located close to each other, and a similar situation is observed for the 395 nm and 405 nm LEDs. Consequently, the spectral power distributions of the 365 nm–375 nm and 395 nm–405 nm groups overlap considerably. However, as illustrated in figure 3, this spectral overlap does not adversely affect the overall spectral power distribution. Ultimately, the data confirms the successful integration of 14 discrete channels, demonstrating specific spectral peaks that span the UVC to the UVA regions.

3.3. Burn-in characteristics

All measurement results over the 110 h aging period were used to calculate the drift in optical output and the shift of wavelength peaks.

Figure 4 presents the long-term change of the total output over 66 measurement series (approximately 110 h), along with one representative LED from each UV spectral region, as LEDs within each region exhibit similar characteristic behavior.

An initial behavior is observed during the early hours, followed by a gradual and consistent decrease in the signal level. After the initial measurement series, the drift remains relatively slow and smooth, indicating stable long-term operation of the system. The overall drift observed over the full measurement

Figure 3. Spectral irradiance of individual LEDs/LED groups at 50 cm.

Figure 4. Drifts in output over 110 h of aging.

series is $1.36 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$, which is acceptable for ending aging, while deuterium lamps' drift is determined below average $7 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$ after the seasoning process [3]. The UVC LED exhibits an approximately 30% decrease in performance after about 110 h of operation; in contrast, a high-power UVA LED must be operated for more than 1000 h to reach a comparable level of degradation [13]. For AlGaIn-based LEDs, devices designed for the UV-C region require a higher aluminum content. This higher aluminum doping is known to promote an increase in non-radiative recombination around the junction over time. Consequently, UV-C LEDs are expected to degrade more rapidly than UVA LEDs [14].

The temporal characterization of the system, as summarized in table 2, reveals a significant enhancement in the source's stability over the 110 h aging period. Most notably, the optical drift underwent a nearly tenfold reduction, stabilizing at a remarkable $2.37 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in the final stages of the test. These results demonstrate that the system provides a stable optical output.

Moreover, the drift in the optical output corresponding to the individually measured peak wavelengths shown in figure 3 was evaluated over the (2–40) h and (40–110) h measurement periods, and the results are presented in table 3. The drift rates exhibit a clear wavelength dependence, with higher values observed at shorter wavelengths. During the early measurement period (2–40) h, the UVC and

Table 2. The aging behavior of the source.

	Drift of total optical output (h^{-1})	Standard deviation of temperature (%)	Standard deviation of optical output (%)
Between 2 h and 110 h	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-04}$	8.4	0.9
Between 40 h and 110 h	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-04}$	1.7	0.4
Between 96 h and 110 h	$2.37 \cdot 10^{-05}$	1.3	0.2

Table 3. The drift in the optical output corresponding to the individually measured peak wavelengths.

	WL (nm)	Drift (h^{-1}) 2 h-40 h	Drift (h^{-1}) 40 h-110 h
UVC	259.88	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-3}$
UVC	266.67	$4.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$
UVC	270.05	$4.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-3}$
UVB	280.02	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.18 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVB	299.92	$5.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-4.38 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVB	310.94	$-1.04 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5.88 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	327.33	$-1.32 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.37 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	344.87	$4.00 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	349.16	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.19 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	369.97	$-2.27 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.36 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	370.89	$-2.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.70 \cdot 10^{-4}$
UVA	389.91	$-1.82 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-3.95 \cdot 10^{-5}$
UVA	399.94	$-1.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-6.27 \cdot 10^{-6}$

UVB regions show relatively high positive drift rates, which can be attributed to ongoing aging and stabilization processes of the UV LEDs and associated electronic components. In contrast, the UVA region exhibits smaller drift values during the same period, indicating a faster stabilization behavior and a lower sensitivity to aging-related effects. This behavior is consistent with the more established nature and thermal robustness of UVA LED technology. In the later measurement period (40–110) h, the drift rates decrease significantly across all spectral regions, reaching the order of 10^{-4} h^{-1} or lower. This substantial reduction in drift demonstrates that the source has reached a stable operating regime, with minimal long-term variation, making it suitable for extended measurements and radiometric applications.

The wavelength shift of the source was analyzed by comparing seven peak positions identified in the 2nd hour and 110th hour measurements directly obtained from spectroradiometer, as shown in figure 5. Due to the failure of the 285 nm LEDs, only six peak positions are observed in the 66th measurement. The maximum shift, 0.8 nm is observed in the 265 nm region is attributed to the influence of the 285 nm LED on the combined spectral response. In the UVB region, the peak at 310.5 nm is shifted 0.2 nm in 110 h. In the UVA region, the wavelength shift is limited to about 0.1 nm for all peaks except the 350 nm LED. Owing to the dome structure of the 350 nm LED and its gradual yellowing over time, a relatively large peak shift of approximately 0.4 nm is observed for this wavelength.

3.4. Spectral irradiance at 50 cm

The spectral irradiance of the source is presented in figure 6. For comparative purposes, the spectral irradiance values of a standard FEL lamp are also included in the same figure. The 285 nm LED units malfunctioned during the measurements, the irradiance in this specific region stayed above the $1 \text{ mW} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1}$ target. This is explained by the contribution of the spectral overlap from adjacent LED groups, which supported the irradiance level at 285 nm despite the faulty channel.

Due to the use of narrowband LEDs, multiple spectral peaks appear across the entire wavelength range. The peaks in the UVA region are more pronounced than those in the UVB and UVC regions. This is primarily because LEDs operating in the UVB and UVC regions inherently exhibit lower optical power compared to those in the UVA region. The reduced peak intensities in the UVB and UVC regions are attributed to current technological limitations, as the emission efficiency and output power of UVB and UVC LEDs have not yet reached the levels achievable in the UVA region. Nevertheless, recent advances in AlGaIn-based LED technologies have led to notable improvements in emission efficiency, particularly in the UVB and UVC spectral ranges [15, 16]. These developments contribute to a gradual reduction of the performance gap between different UV regions.

Importantly, the tunable nature of the source provides additional flexibility for spectral optimization. Since the UVB and UVC LEDs are already operated close to their practical limits (e.g. at approximately

Figure 5. The shifts in wavelength peaks.

Figure 6. Irradiance level at 50 cm.

70% of their maximum drive current), further enhancement in these regions is constrained. Therefore, a smoother spectral distribution can be achieved by reducing the drive current of the UVA LEDs, thereby lowering their dominant peak intensities and improving overall spectral uniformity. Alternatively, users may select different operating conditions to realize customized spectral profiles depending on the application requirements. While the FEL lamp provides a continuous blackbody-like spectrum, the discrete but high-intensity peaks of the proposed UV-LED source offer superior irradiance levels in UV regions, where FEL’s output is traditionally limited. As shown in figure 6 in UVC region, the LED output is nearly nine times higher than the FEL source. This trend continues in the UVA and UVB regions by a factor of more than four.

3.5. Instability and reproducibility

Table 4 summarizes the typical stability and reproducibility performance of conventional transfer light sources reported in the literature. To enable a direct comparison and assess whether the proposed LED-based source meets or exceeds these benchmarks, a detailed stability and reproducibility analysis was performed.

Table 4. Transfer light source characteristics.

Source type	Stability	Reproducibility	Uniformity	References
Tungsten filament lamp	< 0.1%.	< 0.2%	—	[17, 18]
Deuterium lamp	$3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$	< 0.4%	< 1% over the 60 mm-diameter area.	[3]
LED based source in visible region	< 0.1%	high	Uniform	[19]
Tunable broadband UV LED source	0.6% to 1.2%	0.2% to 1.8%	1.2%	

Figure 7. Instability of the source.

The stability and reproducibility characteristics of the source were evaluated using the measurement data obtained after 96 h (56. Measurement series) of operation. The earlier measurement intervals exhibited higher drift, larger amplitude variations, and significant temperature fluctuations, indicating that the source had not yet reached stable operating conditions. After 96 h, the source demonstrated substantially improved stability, with reduced drift, lower amplitude standard deviation, and minimal temperature variation. This behavior indicates that the source had reached a steady-state thermal and radiometric regime. Therefore, only the data acquired after 96 h were considered for the characterization of the source, as they more accurately represent its stable performance and exclude initial aging and temperature deviation effects. The instability of the optical output was determined by calculating the standard deviation of each individual series. For each 2 h series, the instability was evaluated starting from three distinct time points: the initial reading, 30th-minute, and 60th-minute. Each of the 66 measurement series was analyzed using this method, and it was determined that the final ten series exhibited similar instability behavior. One representative example from these series is presented in figure 7.

The calculation from the first reading, the instability exceeds 1% below 300 nm, while the rest of the spectrum varies up to 0.5%. Starting from the 30th-minute reading improves instability, though it remains relatively high below 300 nm and the worst stability is 0.6%.

To analyze the temporal instability, the instability values of the UV source for the UVA, UVB, and UVC spectral regions, are also evaluated over four consecutive 30 min intervals during a two-hour measurement period given in table 5. The instability is highest during the initial 30 min for all spectral regions, with the most pronounced values observed in the UVB and UVC ranges. As the operating time increases, a clear reduction in instability is observed, indicating improved temporal stability after the warm-up phase. In particular, the UVA region exhibits relatively low instability throughout the measurement period, remaining nearly constant after the first 30 min. In contrast, the UVB and UVC regions show a more significant improvement between the first and subsequent time intervals, after which the instability values converge and remain within a narrower range. These results suggest that the source reaches a stable operating condition after approximately 30 min of operation.

The relatively higher instability observed in the UVC region can be explained by the lower spectral responsivity of the spectrometer at short wavelengths and the lower output level of the source, which together increase the impact of measurement noise on the signal.

Table 5. Average instability values of the source for different spectral regions and time intervals.

	Instability (%)			
	(0–30) min	(30–60) min	(60–90) min	(90–120) min
UVA (315–400) nm	0.23	0.13	0.13	0.13
UVB (280–315) nm	0.58	0.31	0.29	0.28
UVC (255–280) nm	0.51	0.39	0.34	0.36

Figure 8. The reproducibility of the source.

Reproducibility was investigated as the variability between measurement series with the influence of the warm-up phase excluded. Accordingly, reproducibility was determined using the spectral optical output measured after a 30 min warm-up period. The mean of the data after 30th-minute was calculated separately for each of the last ten series. The reproducibility was then determined as the standard deviation of these ten series-mean values and expressed as a percentage of their overall mean. The results are presented in figure 8. Across the majority of the spectral range, reproducibility remains within the interval of approximately 0.2%–1.8%.

The maximum reproducibility was observed to be 4.0% at 250 nm. However, this wavelength lies outside the defined spectral range of the source. Immediately beyond this wavelength, the reproducibility improves significantly. At 255 nm, which represents the lower spectral limit of the source, the reproducibility was determined to be approximately 1.8%. The relatively low LED radiant output at short wavelengths, together with reduced detector responsivity in this region, may have contributed to the increased relative variability. In the 270 nm–320 nm range, some local spectral fluctuations are observed; however, reproducibility generally remains below 1.8%. In the 320 nm–380 nm region, the values improve further and have an average value of 0.5%. A slight increase is observed around 400 nm, although the reproducibility values remain low overall.

3.6. Instability of LED currents

Each current of the individual LEDs and LED groups is monitored by an internal current-sensing circuit on the multi channel current driver board. The measured current is read by the control electronics and transferred to the computer through the USB communication interface, where it is displayed by the control software.

The optical output of the LEDs is affected by the instability of their driving current. During the measurements, LED currents were recorded to analyze their instability. The calculated current stability values for individual LEDs and LED groups are presented in figure 9. The current instability of the 265 nm LEDs was found to exceed 1.1%. While the instability values of the other LEDs remained below 0.5%. This indicates that the current instability of the 265 nm LEDs may contribute to the deviations in the source instability (figure 7) and in the source reproducibility (figure 8) observed below 300 nm.

Table 6 presents the current and temperature instabilities for different spectral regions over successive 30 min intervals. The results show that both current and temperature instabilities are highest during the

Figure 9. Current instability of LEDs.

Table 6. Current and temperature instability for different spectral regions and time intervals.

	Current and temperature instability (%)			
	(0–30) min	(30–60) min	(60–90) min	(90–120) min
UVA (315–400) nm	0.34	0.29	0.27	0.28
UVB (280–315) nm	0.31	0.22	0.14	0.13
UVC (255–280) nm	1.31	0.81	0.38	0.35
Temperature	2.2	1.2	1.2	1.1

initial (0–30) min period and decrease progressively with time, indicating thermal stabilization of the LED system. The UVC region (255 nm–280 nm) exhibits the largest current instability, reaching 1.31% in the first 30 min and decreasing to 0.35% after (90–120) min, whereas the UVA (315 nm–400 nm) and UVB (280 nm–315 nm) regions remain below 0.35% after the initial interval. Similarly, temperature instability decreases from 2.2% in the first 30 min to approximately 1.1%–1.2% in later intervals. The simultaneous reduction in current and temperature fluctuations suggests that thermal regulation and electrical stabilization are the primary factors influencing the observed optical instability, particularly in the short-wavelength UVC region.

3.7. Spatial non-uniformity

In order to achieve high UV irradiance levels, the light source was developed using an array of 79 LEDs. During the design phase, UVA LEDs were utilized in fewer numbers relative to UVB and UVC LEDs; this was strategically decided due to their significantly higher radiant intensity and the necessity for effective thermal management, as UVA components generate higher heat loads. The remaining LEDs were distributed homogeneously across a PCB with a diameter of 10 cm. To characterize the spatial distribution and uniformity of the output, a 6 cm × 7 cm area centered around the optical axis at 500 mm distance from the source was scanned using a spectroradiometer with the input optics of 8 mm in diameter. Figure 10 illustrates the variations in total irradiance alongside the specific distributions for each UV region. Based on the scanning data, the non-uniformity of the total irradiance within the target area was calculated to be approximately 1.2%.

3.8. Temperature sensitivity

Characterization measurements of the source were initially conducted at 25 °C, followed by temperature sensitivity measurements. The total irradiance values at the different temperature were normalized to the irradiance value at 25 °C as shown in figure 11 where error bars represent the standard deviation of the total irradiance level. The results show that as the temperature increases, the total irradiance consistently decreases. The measurements at 31 °C demonstrated that the source maintains its most stable output at this temperature because of the lowest standard deviation of the total irradiance level.

3.9. Uncertainty budget

The uncertainty budget for the developed tunable UV LED source is summarized in table 7 across three representative wavelengths (275 nm, 310 nm, and 375 nm). The results indicate that the combined standard uncertainty ($k = 1$) ranges from 2.3% in the UVA region to 4.1% in the UVC region.

The higher uncertainty observed at 275 nm (4.1%) is primarily attributed to the reduced responsiveness of the spectrometer in the deep UV range, as well as the inherent characterization challenges associated with UVC LEDs. In contrast, the source demonstrates better performance in the UVA region

Table 7. Uncertainty budget.

Uncertainty Components	Unit	275 nm	310 nm	375 nm
Instability	(%)	0.6	0.2	0.1
Spectrometer responsivity	(%)	3.5	2.5	1.3
Spectrometer wavelength accuracy	(%)	0.02	0.0	0.0
LED current instability	(%)	0.5	0.1	0.4
LED temperature instability	(%)	1.4	1.4	1.4
Reproducibility	(%)	0.7	0.3	0.2
Spatial non-uniformity	(%)	1.2	1.2	1.2
Combined uncertainty ($k = 1$)	(%)	4.1	3.1	2.3

(375 nm), with a combined uncertainty of only 2.3%, driven by superior LED stability and higher detector sensitivity.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a tuneable broadband UV LED source covering the spectral range from 255 nm to 405 nm was successfully designed, implemented, and characterized as a potential alternative to conventional incandescent and discharge-based irradiance transfer standards. By integrating 79 commercially available LEDs across 14 wavelength channels, the source achieves continuous spectral coverage with spectral irradiance levels exceeding $1 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{nm}^{-1}$ over the entire spectral range.

Comprehensive aging and characterization measurements were conducted over approximately 110 h, demonstrating that the source reaches a stable operating regime after an initial warm-up and stabilization phase. After a 30 min warm-up period, the source exhibits excellent temporal stability. The 30 min warm-up period is sufficient to bring the instability below 0.6% for wavelengths above 300 nm, ensuring reliable measurements for long-term applications. Reproducibility remains below 1.8% for most wavelengths.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the developed tuneable broadband UV LED source meets the essential requirements for laboratory irradiance measurements and UV metrology applications. While further improvements in optical homogenization and long-term stability of short-wavelength LEDs are desirable, the presented system provides a flexible, stable, and energy-efficient platform with strong potential to replace conventional UV standard sources in future radiometric applications.

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Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

Author contributions

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Data curation (equal), Formal analysis (equal), Investigation (equal), Methodology (equal), Writing – original draft (equal), Writing – review & editing (equal)

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Data curation (supporting)

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